

Daring or Dangerous: A Political Determination on Drugs

AP Seminar

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Abstract

This paper contains a political determination and analysis of the status of drugs in the current world. Politics and legalities overlap with almost every facet of life, and reflects that fact while still attempting to stay true to the pertinence and import of the political sphere. Considered is the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic and the problem of microdosing as well as the similarities between tobacco, alcohol, and drugs. The political and historical significance of drugs and their impact on people of all walks of life are critically analyzed.

Keywords: Drugs, Addiction, Covid-19, Legalities, Political, Historical

Introduction

Drugs are a topic heavily debated in our modern world. The negative ramifications are among the first things offered in this conversation, followed succinctly by the numerous benefits. Among the most common of arguments is for a compromise between the current status and one of the other two options, leaving the question to seem to be very simple: decriminalization or legalization. However, this is not the case. Increasing concerns include the rapid uptick of popularity as much of the younger generation seems to move away from alcohol consumption and move towards one of the two most ‘similar’ alternatives, either alcohol or some form of addictive nicotine. According to Andrew Armstrong, a specialist in the field, this affects a much larger variety of people than originally thought, coming to impact those from all facets and walks of life (Armstrong, 2003). One of the most affected by this sudden change in drug and drug access is the systems that are invested in the regularization of these drugs. This problem is one that is complex, yet incredibly imperative. The recent fentanyl crisis across many areas in North America are a prime example of this according to PhD Dr. Daniulaityte, who has a specialization in public health (Daniulaityte et al., 2023). In fact, in Canada alone, about 3% of people have used either cocaine, ecstasy, a form of methamphetamine, a type of hallucinogen, or heroin as of 2023, mentions Carberg, founder of Addiction Help (Carberg & Miller, 2023). As drug misuse continues, more and more individuals may become prey to the harsh reality of addiction, and as a natural response, people look to the government to solve the issue of drug use in society.

During Times of Crisis: Covid-19

Drugs are a topic heavily debated in our modern time, and they are not one that has decreased in relevancy by any means. From a political standpoint, current events are always in the midst of the ideal sweeping changes of legislation to be made. There are a variety of claims

to be made about the drug crisis during the height of the Covid-19 pandemic, and interestingly, many of them seem to find contradictions in one another. Natalia Chacon, a Master of Public Health (MPH) graduate with over four years of experience in similar topics, argues that the COVID-19 pandemic has worsened the conditions of substance abuse, offering a number of reasons for why this may be, namely due to United States governmental support declining in these areas to focus more on other ones (Chacon, 2021). On the side converse to Chacon, PhD Ryan McNeil with a focus on substance abuse argues that in the case of Canada's comparatively left-leaning British Columbia, this was a problem that was foreseen. This was counteracted by providing measures of legalized access to prescription alternatives, which worked to cushion the otherwise much more devastating hit that happened in other places (McNeil et al., 2022). The National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA) corroborates both these theories, cementing that in the United States as a whole, there is no clear one directional effect and rather that there have been huge changes in both direction at varying times of the pandemic (National Institute on Drug Abuse, 2023). Politics seems to be incredibly divided on the topic of drug usage during the pandemic, which may find its attribution in the spectrum of ideological differences.

Comparative Analysis: Tobacco, Alcohol, Etc.

A glance upon the political lens draws similarities between drugs and other similar substances. Addiction is often seen and treated in familiar fashion across the board when comparing conditions such as alcoholism and addiction to tobacco or to methamphetamine. Unable to be truly separated from historical commentary, Rachel Ann Barry from the Center for Tobacco Control Research notes the political treatment of marijuana and tobacco and their immense overlap. She explains in detail that both substances often have shared markets and share a place in the argumentation of documentation, especially through the last few decades

(Barry et al., 2014). Her comments seem to draw glaring contrast with the reputed organization of substance abuse; the Institute for Behavior and Health. They go as far as to state that the commonly argued reforms may worsen the problem of drug usage and addiction as a whole (Institute for Behavior and Health, n.d.). The Institute for Behavior and Health even makes a direct reference to tobacco in specific and saying that tobacco is an incredibly poor model for legalization, motioning to the tax revenues gained and the comparatively low costs in terms of social care. Alan Steel mentions a similar concept to the Institute for Behavior and Health in an article published in *Drugs and Alcohol Today*, his compromise-based mindset. He analyzes the potential repercussions of switching the sale of drugs to a method similar to an alcohol license, noting that this may be very likely to decrease damages done, although there is still a small chance of the opposite (increasing damages) may have happened (Steel, 2006).

Less May Not Be More: Microdosing and Cap Theory

A challenge that has recently been increasing in relevance has been something small. This isn't to say that the outrage is without reason, it most certainly is. Both sides of the political spectrum (assuming that one is operating on a spectrum of liberalism to conservatism) share a sense of disagreement when faced with the problem of microdosing and the tangentially related problem of smaller amounts of drug possession. As per Health Law Assistant Professor Mason Marks, microdosing refers to the usage of small amounts of drugs on alternative days of a set schedule, which typically abides area law but may still breach into dangerous territory (Marks et al., 2023). In contrast, British Columbia struggled with small amounts of usage that did not constitute under the typically used definition of microdosing. As per Craig McCulloch on VOA news, which provides easily accessible news coverage for much of the world, the area has placed an exemption for possession of drugs up until the amount of 2.5 grams, and has the approval of

Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau (McCulloch, 2023). This concept is supported by the cap theory discussed by Ali Farihah, the scientific lead for the Ontario Canadian Research Initiative in Substance Misuse within the Institute of Mental Health Policy Research (IMHPR). She explains the concept of an amount that seems to be the viable limit before much of the legislation has decided that the situation has gone too far to avoid (Farihah et al., 2017).

Conclusion

The concerns of the legal and political world display an all-encompassing look at the complexities of drugs and their current status in society. When analyzing drugs in North America, one must seek to take heed to follow the U.S. Department of Justice's advice and remember who drugs disproportionately affect much of the time (Duke & Gross, 1996). The effect of drugs also varies widely depending on whom you ask, from being casual recreation to being treated as a necessity, as displayed by Alexis S. Hammond of the Behavioral Pharmacology Research Unit (BPRU) (Hammond, 2021). In the end, one should remember to keep in mind that no action has a singular result. It instead ripples outward and affects an ocean of individuals.

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